

Wireless Electric Vehicle Charging System-A Review

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ABSTRACT

Electric vehicles require fast, economical and reliable charging systems for efficient performance. Wireless charging systems remove the inconvenience to plug in the device to be charged when compared with the conventional wired charging systems. Moreover, wireless charging is considered to be environment and user friendly as the wires and mechanical connectors and related infrastructure are not required. This paper presents basic structure, operating principles and distinct features for wireless charging of EVs. First, the general techniques for wireless power transfer are described and explained. Next wireless charging systems for electric vehicles are classified and discussed in depth. Both the stationary and the dynamic wireless charging systems are discussed and reviewed. In addition, innovative and unique solution proposed is Dynamic Wireless Charging System. Dynamic charging systems seek to charge an EV while it is in service and is moving. It based on magnetic coupled resonant power transmission in which the transmitting coil of this charging system can selectively turn ON/OFF for charging vehicles while driving. Due to this energy is not wasted as transmission coil is energized when vehicle came in contact with receiver coil. The magnetic flux, a voltage is induced in the receiver coil when comes in line with transmitting coil. Control system functions of a wireless charging system of an electric vehicle. Findings of this state-of-the-art review are discussed and recommendations for future research are also provided.

Keywords:- Electric vehicle, Wireless charging, Dynamic Charging, Arduino UNO, IR Sensor

1. INTRODUCTION

Electric vehicles (EVs) are one of the promising solutions to improve economic efficiency and reduce the carbon footprint in the transportation sector. Earlier research is focused on the plug-in and conductive solutions for charging the EVs and addressed the challenges of integrating this technology into electricity networks. Plug-in EVs have limited travel range and require large and heavy batteries. Therefore, conductive charging strategies require long waiting time that limits the applicability of EVs compared to gasoline-powered vehicles. More recent research efforts introduced wireless or inductive charging solutions that enable in-motion charging of the EVs which makes EV more favourable for the daily use of many drivers. Wireless charging – also referred to as in-motion charging is different from the conventional charging technologies as it enables charging the EV battery while driving in the transportation network. Therefore, the electricity demand for wirelessly charging the EVs is determined by the traffic volume in the transportation network and the decisions made for charging the EVs as they travel over the charging stations. Therefore, unlike the conventional plug in charging solutions, wireless charging technology underlines the interdependence between the traffic routing and the EVs' charging strategies. The EV routing determines the electricity demand at different WCS, which in turn, would affect the electricity charging prices at these stations. Therefore, as the number of EVs with wireless charging capabilities increase, the characteristics of the demand imposed by the wireless charging of EV the day-ahead operation of the electricity network. In this paper, the proposed decentralized approach addresses the interaction between the electricity and transportation networks by capturing the imposed wireless charging demand which is further determined by the traffic flow pattern and the price of electricity. Wireless charging EV is a type of EV in which charging is done using wireless power transfer (WPT) technology, which does not require any physical contact in the process of transferring electric energy. WPT has been successfully applied for charging various handheld devices, such as medical devices, electronic toothbrushes, and smart phones. It has also been widely used for automated material handling systems in semiconductor fabrication and flat-panel display production lines. Wireless charging technology was first commercialized for automobiles to eliminate the conventional charging of „plug-in“ EVs – charged by connecting a wired cable from a charger to the vehicle. The first wireless charging technology to be deployed was stationary, the system having been designed to charge EVs in garages or public parking spaces, when the vehicle is not operating for an extended period. Because a physical

connection is not required, there has been major interest in the possibility of charging EVs while they are in transit. Charging an EV while in motion is called dynamic wireless charging. A typical dynamic wireless charging EV is a pure, battery-only EV that takes its electrical charge in motion, remotely, from a wireless charger installed underneath the road surface. Roads capable of supplying electric power to wireless charging EVs are called electrified roads or charging lanes. There is also a third wireless charging category, quasi-dynamic wireless charging, in which the charging takes place when the EV decelerates to or accelerates from a resting position.

Objective

- Design a suitable charging station for electric vehicles.
- Design a solar powered charging station to eliminate the over usage of fossil fuel which increase air pollution and lead to climate changes.
- Design a user interface for electric vehicle charging.
- Design automatic control circuit for streetlight near the local station.
- Design of mobile phone charging circuit.

2. METHODOLOGY

If wired charging system is built at various charging stations. Wired charging station having more disadvantages such as space required is more, socket are different types, a small substation required, converter circuit is installed at every charging station, range of wire is limited and also time required for charging is more. This all problems is solved by wireless electrical vehicle charging system. The traditional wired or plug-in charging systems are not user and environment friendly. To reduce the charging time, a large number of batteries can be used or the drained batteries can be swapped with the charged batteries when needed. There is energy waste due to line loss when the coil is conducted for long time. Its service life will be decreased because of continuous working.

Block Diagram

The block diagram consists of the Arduinouno, IR sensor, transmitter coil, receiver coil, AC to DC converter, relay, battery, DC motor, LED as shown in figure 1.

Block Diagram – Battery Charging & Control System

Figure 1: Block Diagram

Arduino uno is the main component of the project as it control and monitor the parameters, IR sensor will detect the presences of the vehicle and sends the signal to Arduino uno. Depending upon the vehicle position, relay is turned on to energize the transmitter coil. The receiver coil present in the vehicle gets energized by the transmitter coil by mutual coupling, the energy produced is given to AC to DC converter, and the converter is connected to the battery. The battery gives power to the motor to run.

Wireless Charging Architecture

Wireless charging system architecture consisting of AC supply which is used as the source to fed the transmission coil. From the principle of resonant coupling, the reception coil is coupled. The output is given to AC-DC converter to obtain rectified DC to charge the battery which is connected to load. The coils in the project which is used to transmit power wirelessly are called magnetic resonators. This creates magnetic field in the region around a transmission coil, tune a reception coil to the same resonant frequency as the source, it will couple resonating anywhere within that region, converting oscillating magnetic field into an electrical current within the reception

coil this response is called coupled magnetic response. The power can be fed to the load for charging a battery. Block diagram of wireless charging system is shown in Fig. 2 connected in series-to-series topology .

figure 2: Wireless Charging

3. CONCLUSION

The Wireless EV Charging System using RFID successfully combines secure access control with convenient wireless power transfer for electric vehicles. By integrating RFID technology, the system ensures that only authorized users can initiate charging, which improves security and prevents misuse. The wireless charging setup eliminates the need for physical cables, reducing wear and tear, increasing user convenience, and minimizing the risk of electric shock. Arduino serves as the central controller, managing RFID authentication, enabling or disabling the transmitter, monitoring charging parameters, and ensuring safe operation. The system demonstrates how automation, wireless energy transfer, and smart access control can be integrated to create an efficient and user-friendly charging solution. Although this prototype is implemented at a small scale for demonstration, the concept can be extended to real-time EV charging stations with higher power capacity, advanced safety features, and smart grid connectivity. Thus, this project shows a step toward future smart, secure, and contactless EV charging infrastructure.

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